

Oxidation of Diketones. Vanadium(V) Oxidation of Acetyl Acetone and Benzoyl Acetone†

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IN continuation to our earlier report on oxidation of compounds containing active methylene group by vanadium(V) in acid medium¹, the oxidation kinetics of acetyl and benzoyl acetones in sulphuric acid are further extended in the present communication.

Experimental

Ammonium metavanadate (Reidel) was dissolved in appropriate concentration of sulphuric acid (B.D.H., A.R.) to prepare vanadium(V) solution. The ketones were purified by distillation and their solutions were used in glacial acetic acid. Other chemicals employed were of AnalaR grade.

Adequate concentrations of the reactants were mixed and the rate of oxidation was followed by estimating the unconsumed V^V in aliquotes withdrawn at regular intervals by titrating against ferrous ammonium sulphate solution using *N*-phenylanthranilic acid as an indicator.

Results and Discussion

Kinetic studies were arranged under the conditions [H₂SO₄] and [ketone] ≫ [V^V] at constant ionic strength. The results can be summarised as follow :

- (i) The reactions are first order in V^V as the plots of log (a-x) vs time are linear. Moreover, the first order rate constants for different initial concentrations of V^V for a particular [ketone] and [H⁺] are almost the same proving the first order dependence in V^V (Tables 1 and 2).
- (ii) The pseudo first order rate constant increases with increase in [ketone]. The plots of log k₁ vs log [ketone] are linear with slopes nearly unity (acetyl acetone =1.12, and benzoyl acetone =1.01) and also the constancy in second order rate constants (k₂), thereby indicating that the order is one in ketones. A positive intercept on the Y-axis of the plots

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON REACTANTS AT 50°

[V ^V] × 10 ³ M	[HOAc] = 40% (v/v) [AA] × 10 ³ M	[H ⁺] M	μ M	k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	k ₂ × 10 ⁴ l mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
2.50	10.00	2.0	2.01	12.40	—
4.00	10.00	2.0	2.01	11.70	—
5.00	10.00	2.0	2.01	11.76	—
6.66	10.00	2.0	2.01	11.77	1.17
10.00	10.00	2.0	2.01	12.18	—
6.66	5.00	2.0	2.01	6.37	1.27
6.66	6.00	2.0	2.01	8.36	1.26
6.66	13.30	2.0	2.01	17.37	1.30
6.66	20.00	2.0	2.01	25.25	1.26
6.66	25.00	2.0	2.01	32.05	1.28
6.66	10.00	1.5	3.51	17.21	1.14
6.66	10.00	2.0	3.51	22.24	1.11
6.66	10.00	2.5	3.51	28.12	1.12
6.66	10.00	3.0	3.51	34.21	1.14
6.66	10.00	3.5	3.51	40.02	1.14

AA = Acetyl acetone.

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON REACTANTS AT 50°

[V ^V] × 10 ³ M	[HOAc] = 43.3% (v/v) [BA] × 10 ³ M	[H ⁺] M	μ M	k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	k ₂ × 10 ⁴ l mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
2.50	3.33	3.0	3.01	13.32	—
3.33	3.33	3.0	3.01	13.37	4.00
4.00	3.33	3.0	3.01	13.94	—
5.00	3.33	3.0	3.01	13.90	—
10.00	3.33	3.0	3.01	14.29	—
3.33	0.50	3.0	3.01	2.00	4.00
3.33	1.00	3.0	3.01	3.95	3.95
3.33	2.00	3.0	3.01	7.36	3.68
3.33	2.50	3.0	3.01	9.53	3.81
3.33	4.00	3.0	3.01	15.92	3.98
3.33	3.33	2.5	4.51	25.11	1.00
3.33	3.33	3.0	4.51	35.92	1.19
3.33	3.33	3.5	4.51	42.91	1.21
3.33	3.33	4.0	4.51	47.51	1.18
3.33	3.33	4.5	4.51	56.23	1.24

BA = Benzoyl acetone.

between k₁⁻¹ and [ketone]⁻¹ gives an evidence of complex formation between V^V and ketones. Similar observations have been reported^{1,2} in the oxidation of other ketones by V^V.

- (iii) Concentration of H₂SO₄ was varied to study the effect of [H⁺] on the rates of the reactions (Tables 1 and 2). The plots of log k₁ vs log [H⁺] are linear with slopes 1.13 and 1.16 for acetyl acetone and benzoyl acetone, respectively. Hammett plots of log k₁ vs H₀ are linear with slopes less than unity (acetyl acetone =0.41, benzoyl acetone=0.45) which are comparable to those reported for the oxidation of methyl ethyl ketone³ and citric acid⁴.
- (iv) The effect of change in dielectric constant of the medium by changing the percentage-composition of acetic acid in solvent mixture shows a decrease in the rate of oxidation. The linear plots between log k₁ and 1/D with positive slopes suggest the reactions to be of ion-dipole type. Addition of NaHSO₄ increases the rate, whereas Na₂SO₄ decreases it.

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Mechanism: The parent species of V^V in mineral acids is considered⁴ to be VO_2^+ . At slightly higher acid concentration VO_2^+ is assumed to be in equilibrium with $V(OH)_2^{2+}$ (equation 1)

The marked colour of sulphuric acid solution of V^V suggests that one HSO_4^- may be incorporated in the active species⁵⁻⁷ which may be represented as $V(OH)_2HSO_4^+$ (equation 2). The effect of the addition of $NaHSO_4$ and Na_2SO_4 lends support to the equilibrium,

Polymerisation test with acrylonitrile is positive, indicating the formation of free radical intermediates and also that V^V acts as one-electron oxidant.

The experimental results, therefore, lead to the following rate expression.

At constant $[V^V]_T$

$$k_{obs} = \frac{K_1' K_2 k_1 [\text{ketone}] [H_2SO_4]}{1 + K_1' [H_2SO_4] + K_1' K_2 [\text{ketone}] [H_2SO_4]} \quad (7)$$

According to Wells and Kuritsyn⁸, the equilibrium constant for the formation of $V(OH)_2^{2+}$ is much less than one. Therefore, it can be assumed that K_1' is very small as compared to $K_2 k_1$.

$$\frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \frac{1}{X [\text{ketone}]} + \frac{1}{k_1} \quad (8)$$

where $X = K_1' K_2 k_1 [H_2SO_4]$ at constant concentration of H_2SO_4 . The plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{ketone}]$ are linear with positive intercept on Y-axis.

Since K_1' is less than unity, $[K_1' K_2]$ is also less than one and hence, the equation (7) may be expressed as

$$k_{obs} = k_1 K_1' K_2 [\text{ketone}] [H_2SO_4] \quad (9)$$

and at constant concentration of sulphuric acid

$$k_{obs} = K' [\text{ketone}]$$

where, $K' = K_1' K_2 k_1 [H_2SO_4]$.

The plots of k_{obs} vs $[\text{ketone}]$ should be linear passing through the origin.

Values of entropy of activation too confirm the C-H fission in the mechanistic steps. Kinetic results show that the reactivity of benzoyl acetone is more

than acetyl acetone. This may be due to the conjugation effect.

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Kinetics of Oxidation of Diphenyl Methane by Selenium Dioxide

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SELENIUM dioxide has been used as an oxidant in the study of kinetics of oxidation of some ketones¹⁻⁴, though similar studies with diphenylmethane have not been made so far. The rate of oxidation of diphenyl methane by chromic acid in glacial acetic acid is extremely rapid at first, but soon slackens and stops almost entirely after a few hours though both diphenylmethane and Cr^{VI} remain in solution⁵. Literature survey shows that much work has been done on the mechanism of oxidation of olefins by selenium dioxide⁶⁻¹², but it seems that no attention has been given to the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of diphenylmethane and related hydrocarbons by selenium dioxide. These have prompted us to study the kinetics of oxidation of diphenylmethane by selenium dioxide to obtain the information on the mechanism of oxidation.

In continuation of our recent interest in the kinetics of oxidation of organic compounds containing active methylene group by selenium dioxide¹³⁻¹⁴, we report, in this note, the kinetics of oxidation of diphenylmethane by selenium